

Cited reference

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Note to readers

To save on costs, the IRRN is now being published three times a year: April, August, and December. We have also discontinued the IRRN sections on news about research collaboration and announcements. The material previously covered in these sections is now included in the *Rice Reporter*.

Pest resistance—insects

Preliminary evidence of aphid resistance in transgenic plants

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Sap-sucking insect pests (mainly Homoptera) can severely damage rice crops and also transmit virus diseases. Promising results have already been achieved with transgenic plants expressing the *Bacillus thuringiensis* (*Bt*) delta-endotoxin gene and proteinase inhibitor genes, which protect plants from Lepidoptera and Coleoptera insect pests, but are not effective against Homoptera insects. Information from this study, which describes pea lectin (*P-lec*) transgenic tobacco plants showing apparent aphid resistance, may be valuable for controlling rice Homoptera insect pests.

Plant expression plasmid constructed. We cloned and identified the *P-lec* gene as described by Liu et al (1995). A *HindIII/SacI* fragment from *pBS-lec1*, including 0.9-kb *P-lec* gene, was inserted into mini Ti-plasmid pK7-1, regulated by CaMV35S promoter in the 5'-end and *rbcS* Poly(A) signal in the 3'-end. The recombinant was

then transferred into *Agrobacterium tumefaciens* LBA4404 by electroporation.

Plant transformation. Leaf discs of tobacco line NC89 were transformed via *A. tumefaciens*. Transformants were selected using kanamycin, and the transgenic plants were confirmed using Npt-II assay.

Bioassay on transgenic plants. Young transgenic tobacco plants and control tobacco plants (4-5 leaves) were individually infested on the top leaves with 80 peach aphids (*Myzus persicae*). Aphid population density was calculated 4 and 6 wk after infestation and used to assign the resistance score (see table).

We evaluated aphid resistance (divided into four resistance levels) based on density of aphid population on the top leaves. The ratio of plants with high resistance to aphids (scores 3 and 4) and the resistance mean in transgenic plants were higher than in the control (see table), indicating that the transgenic plants had better protection from aphids than the control (see figure).

A dramatic difference exists in aphid resistance between the transgenic tobacco and the control, possibly caused by transgenic plants expressing *P-lec*. However, evidence indicating the effect of pea lectin against some sap-sucking insect pests fed

Leaves from transgenic tobacco plant (right) and from control tobacco plant. The photo was taken 6 wk after aphid infestation.

on an artificial diet is not available (Powell et al 1993). Possible explanations for this area) the effects of pea lectin on rice brown planthopper and rice green leafhopper used in Powell's study differed from the effects on aphids, and b) the pea lectin could have lost its antimetabolic activity on Homoptera insects during the artificial diet preparation.

The *P-lec* gene expression plasmid suitable for rice transformation has already been constructed, and the transformation of rice is under way.

Bioassay of transgenic and control tobacco plants.

Score ^a	Weeks after infestation ^b							
	4				6			
	Plants (no.)	Control (%)	Plants (no.)	<i>P-lec</i> (%)	Plants (no.)	Control (%)	Plants (no.)	<i>P-lec</i> (%)
1	21	61.8	8	27.6	27	79.4	8	27.6
2	5	14.9	4	13.8	5	14.7	8	27.6
3	2	5.9	7	24.1	2	5.9	4	13.8
4	6	17.6	10	54.5	0	0.0	9	31.0
Total	34		29		34		29	

^a4 = plants where peach aphid population density on top leaves is less than 2 aphids cm² leaf; 3 = density is between 2 and 5 aphids cm⁻¹ leaf; 2 = density is in the range of 1-50; and 1 = density of more than 10 aphids cm⁻² leaf. ^bData represent percentage of particular plants to total plants infested.

Cited references

- Liu CM, Yu ZY, Zhu Z, Zhou ZL, Xiao GF, and Li XH. 1995. Cloning and sequencing of the pea lectin gene. *Acta Genet. Sin.* 22(4):302-306.
- Powell KS, Gatehouse AMR, Hilder VA, and Gatehouse JA. 1993. Antimetabolic effects of plant lectins and plant and fungal enzymes on the nymphal stages of two important rice pests, *Nilaparvata lugens* and *Nephotettix cincticeps*. *Entomol. Exp. Appl.* 66:119-126. ■